

Studies in Angular Furocoumarins. Part-I. Synthesis of Furo-2',3'-dihydro-2'-methyl-5',4':7,8-Coumarin derivatives.

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Furo-2', 3'-dihydro-5', 4':7,8-coumarin derivatives were synthesised, (i) by developing coumarin ring over preformed dihydrofuran ring and (ii) by forming furan ring over coumarin.

In view of the demonstration that photosensitising activity of furocoumarins vary according to the position and nature of substitution¹ and correlation by Pathak and Fellman² between biological activity and light absorption, we became interested in study of U.V. absorption spectra of furocoumarins substituted at different positions³. We observed³ that reduction of furan ring leads to a bathochromic shift in the spectra of the linear furocoumarins. It was therefore interesting to know whether the same effect is associated with angular furocoumarins also. A search of literature failed to furnish us with any simple unambiguous method for the synthesis of dihydroangular furocoumarins.

Accordingly we devised two different routes for the synthesis of furo-2', 3'-dihydro-2', 3, 4-trimethyl-5', 4': 7, 8-coumarin (IVa) as indicated below. In the first method we started with preformed dihydrofuran ring and the coumarin ring was developed subsequently. In the second method the sequence of the formation of the two heterocyclic rings was reversed. Both methods gave identical product.

- Musajo, Rodighiro, and Caporale, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, 48, 4111; Musajo, Rodighiro, Caporale and Antonello, *ibid.*, 1959, 53, 6222^b.
- Pathak and Fellman, *Nature*, 1960, 185, 362.
- Chatterjee, Chatterjee and Sen, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 2467.

4-Hydroxy-2-methylcoumaran (I) was prepared according to the method of Shamsurin⁴ by converting 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin to 2-allylresorcinol by heating with 20% aqueous caustic soda solution followed by cyclization of the latter, with aqueous hydrobromic acid. This was condensed with ethyl methylacetoacetate(IIa) in the presence of 75% sulfuric acid to furnish furo-2', 3'-dihydro-2', 3, 4-trimethyl-5', 4' : 7, 8-coumarin IVa.

8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (IIIa), prepared by Claisen rearrangement of 7-allyloxy-3, 4-dimethylcoumarin in boiling dimethylaniline, on heating with aqueous hydrobromic acid and purification by vacuum sublimation furnished (IVa). Different furodihydrocoumarins prepared according to method I or method II have been listed in Table II.

Claisen rearrangement of 7-allyloxy coumarin by heating in a sealed tube invariably resulted in the production of a mixture consisting of 8-allyl-7-hydroxycoumarin and furo-2', 3'-dihydro-2'-methyl-5', 4' : 7,8-coumarin (IVh). The mixture was separated with cold 10% caustic soda solution. Structure of (IVh) was confirmed by dehydrogenation with Pd/C to (V) which was found to be identical with furo-2'-methyl-5', 4' : 7,8-coumarin, described by Kaufman⁵.

A study of the Claisen rearrangement of other 7-allyloxy-coumarins having general formula(VI) demonstrated that a mixture also resulted. The cyclized products obtained during rearrangement had same m.p. and mixed m.p. with (IV) synthesized by the other method. The results are described in Table IV.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were repeatedly crystallized from the solvents until sharp and constant melting points were obtained. [7-Allyloxy coumarin derivatives (VIa—VIg) prepared following the procedure of Baker and Lothian⁶, are listed in Table (III)]

8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (IIIa)—7-Allyloxy 3,4-dimethylcoumarin was heated in refluxing dimethylaniline (1 gm. in 3 ml. proportion) for 2 hr. The crystals of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin obtained on cooling melted at 195-196° which required only two crystallizations for purification.

4. Shamsurin, *J. Gen. Chem.*, (USSR), 1944, 14, 881, *Chem. Absr.*, 1945, 39, 3789d.

5. Kaufman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 117.

6. Baker and Lothian, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1935, 628.

The new compounds having general formula III, along with their physical properties and analytical data, are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
Derivatives of 8-Allyl-7-hydroxycoumarin

Compd. III	M. P. °C	Crystn. Solv.	Yield %	Formula	Analysis %			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
(a)	193-196	Ethanol	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃	73.02	72.62	6.13	6.29
(b)	169-170	Ethanol (dil)	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₃	73.75	73.58	6.60	6.28
(c)	148	Methanol (dil)	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₃	74.39	74.09	7.02	6.85
(d)	144-145	Methanol (dil)	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₃	74.97	74.75	7.40	7.67
(e)	182-183	Methanol	66	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₃	77.68	78.01	5.07	5.30
(f)	198	Methanol	60	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₃	78.06	78.27	5.52	5.39
(g)	223	Ethylacetate	71.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.36	74.06	5.83	6.09

Preparation of *Furo-2',3'-dihydro-2',3',4'-trimethyl-5',4':7,8-coumarin (IVa)* Method I. From 4-hydroxy-2-methylcoumaran-1(1) (0.01 mole), ethyl methylacetoacetate (IIa) (0.01 mole) was treated with 75% sulfuric acid (9 ml.). The solution after keeping at 5° for 48 hr. was poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered, washed free from acid, subjected to vacuum sublimation at 180°/0.8 mm. and finally crystallized from ethanol.

Method II. Cyclisation of 8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (IIIa). A mixture of 8-allyl-3,4-dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin(IIIa) (0.03 mole) and 20 ml. of hydrobromic acid (d. 1.48) was heated on water bath for 4 hr. The product was washed with 5% caustic soda and water and finally purified by vacuum sublimation at 180°/0.8 mm.

Different *furodihydrocoumarins* having general formula IV (all new compounds) prepared by methods I and II along with their physical properties and analytical data are listed in Table II.

TABLE II
Derivatives of *furo-2',3'-dihydro-2'-methyl-5',4':7,8-coumarin*

Compd. IV	M. P. °C	Crystn. Solv.	Yield%		Formula	Analysis %			
			Method/I	Method/II		Carbon		Hydrogen	
						Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
(a)	131-132	Ethanol	30	54	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃	73.02	72.69	6.13	6.32
(b)	105-106	Methanol		74	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₃	73.75	73.42	6.60	6.70
(c)	97-98	Ethanol		35	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₃	74.39	74.05	7.02	6.85
(d)	99-100	Methanol	30	80	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₃	74.97	75.36	7.40	7.68
(e)	201-202	Ethylacetate	32	52	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₃	77.68	77.49	5.07	5.39
(f)	101-102	Methanol	33	61	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₃	78.06	78.16	5.52	5.39
(g)	148-144	Ethylacetate	25	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.36	74.65	5.83	6.09

Claisen rearrangement product after heating 7-allyloxycoumarin at 215-220° in a sealed tube² was taken in ether solution and treated with cold 10% caustic soda solution in which the hydroxy compound (IIIh) dissolved. It was isolated by carefully neutralizing

ing the alkaline solution, with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid after crystallization from ethanol had m.p. 165°, lit⁵ m.p. 165-166°. The neutral ethereal layer after removal of (IIb) on evaporation gave (IVh) which on crystallization from ethanol had m.p. 104° (Found: C, 71.08; H, 5.17; $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.99.)

In the same way, (IVi) separated from (IIIi) after heating (VIIi) at 215-220°. It was crystallized from ethanol and had m.p. 116-117°. (Found: C, 72.32; H, 5.80; $C_{13}H_{11}O_3$ requires C, 72.21; H, 5.59). Compounds (IVa-IVi) obtained from Claisen rearrangement had identical m.p. and mixed m.p. with corresponding compound prepared by the previous method.

Results of Claisen rearrangement of compounds (VIa-VIIi), under condition described by Kaufman⁵, are presented in Table IV.

TABLE III

3,4-Alkyl and-aryl derivatives of 7-allyloxy coumarin

Compd. VI	M. P. °C	Crystn. Solvent	Yield %	Formula	Analysis %			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.
(a)	98	Ethylalcohol	96	$C_{14}H_{14}O_3$	73.02	73.20	6.13	6.45
(b)	57	Methanol (dil)	84	$C_{15}H_{16}O_3$	73.75	74.00	6.60	6.55
(c)	55	Methanol (dil)	79	$C_{16}H_{18}O_3$	74.39	74.60	7.02	7.11
(d)	65	Methanol	95	$C_{17}H_{20}O_3$	74.97	75.20	7.40	7.17
(e)	85	Methanol	96.5	$C_{18}H_{24}O_3$	77.68	77.48	5.07	4.92
(f)	84	Petroleum (60-80°)	72	$C_{19}H_{16}O_3$	78.06	78.04	5.52	5.68
(g)	155	Ethylacetate	83.5	$C_{15}H_{14}O_3$	74.63	74.64	5.83	5.55

TABLE IV

Claisen rearrangement products from 7-allyloxy coumarins by heating in sealed tube

Allyloxy compound VI	Claisen product	
	Yield of cyclised product%	Yield of uncyclised product %
(A)	12	55
(i)	15	60
(a)	17.5	55
(b)	38	42
(c)	32	44
(d)	30	37
(e)	10	53
(f)	5	63
(g)	20	20

Para-2'-methyl-5',4':7,8-coumarin (V) A mixture of (IVh 1 g.), Pd/C (10%) (0.5 g) and diphenylether (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 6-8 hr. The catalyst was removed from the hot solution by filtration and the filtrate after removal of solvent by steam distillation, gave (V) which after two crystallizations from methanol had m.p. 152-153°.

Compound (V) prepared according to the method described by Kaufman³ had identical m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above.

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